

Shorter Sukhāvātyūha Sūtra

also known as “Amitābha Sūtra 佛說阿彌陀經”

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Entry tags: Pure Land Buddhism, Chinese Buddhist text, Text, Tibetan Buddhism, Mahayana Buddhism, Chinese Buddhism, Chinese Religion, Japanese Religions, Buddhist Traditions, Korean Religions, Vietnamese Religions, Religious Group, Sanskrit literature

Shorter Sukhāvātyūha Sūtra The Shorter Sukhāvātyūha Sūtra (The Amitābha Sutra; 佛說阿彌陀經; T12, 366) is one of the most fundamental texts for Pure Land Buddhism. It depicts the Sukhāvātī, the wondrous Pure Land of Amitābha, and lists the salvific benefits of being reborn there. Together with the Longer Sukhāvātyūha Sūtra (Infinite Life Sutra; 佛說無量壽經) and the Amitāyus Contemplation Sūtra (Sutra on the Contemplation of the Buddha Immeasurable Life; 佛說觀無量壽經), three sutras constitute the textual pillar of Pure Land Buddhism in East Asia. The sutra starts at the Śākyamuni Buddha's preaching at Jetavana Vihāra, Śrāvastī, to his major disciples and numerous Bodhisattvas. The Buddha introduces Sukhāvātī, the Amitābha's distant pure land of ultimate bliss. In his Western Pure Land, all objects—the land, architecture, adornments, and living beings—are the manifestation of the Dharma. Those who are reborn in Sukhāvātī do not even know the ideas of "evil" and "suffering." The three lower realms of rebirth (animal, hungry ghost, hell) do not exist. Those who are reborn there automatically gain salvific progress from hearing the miraculous and dharmic sounds of its heavenly beings. The Buddha then explains the meanings of the name “Amitayus”/“Amitābha” as the Buddha of immeasurable lifespan and immeasurable light. The Pure Land rebirth requires the person to hear the name of Amitābha and hold this name in mind for seven days, without any disturbance. If at the moment of death, one remains mentally undisturbed, Amitābha and his assemblies will appear to facilitate the person to be reborn in the Pure Land. Then, the sutra moves to the confirmation sections. The sutra offers the praises and endorsements of the Amitābha Buddha by all other Buddhas. It proclaims the Buddhas and Bodhisattvas from the six directions all affirm the inconceivable qualities of Sukhāvātī and exhort the listeners to seek rebirth there. Finally, the sutra emphasizes the importance of faith and bodhisattva vows. The Bodhisattva Vows made by the realized Buddhas, including Amitābha, are the core tenet that affirms the efficacy of Pure Land practices. And compared to all other practices in the Saha World, the Pure Land belief in Amitābha is the most accessible and easy one. In contrast to other Pure Land sutras, the Shorter Sukhāvātyūha Sūtra does not contain the specific forty-eight Bodhisattva vows made by the then Dharmākara Bodhisattva, including to create a field with inconceivable wondrous qualities and who collects the mind to the Amitābha Buddha ten times will be reborn in his land (except who violated five deadly precepts). Based on scholastic commentaries, the path of Pure Land is the “easy path.” In Japan, the power of Amitābha is further labeled as the Tariki (the Power of the Other). Philologically speaking, the origin of the Shorter Sukhāvātyūha Sūtra is still a mystery. The earliest Sanskrit copy was discovered in the Gandhāra region, northern India, and probably composed in the first century CE. Presumably the sutra, as part of the Mahāyāna repertoire, was popular in pre-Islamic Central Asia. The Sanskrit edition was first translated by Max Müller and his cohorts in 1875. It was translated again by Luis O. Gomez in 1996. Since its translation into Chinese, the sutra gradually became the most fundamental text in East Asia. The first Chinese translation was by Kumārajīva in 402. It was subsequently translated again by Guṇabhadra from 454-456 and by Xuanzang in 650. The text was also translated into Tibetan from the ninth century onward. The sutra received extensive commentaries from East Asia monastics. In China, nianfo (being Mindful of the Buddha) became a diffused Buddhist practice that was adopted by many indigenous traditions. In Japan, monastics who favored the text formed Jōdo shū, Jōdo Shinshū, and Nichiren.

Date Range: 100 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Pure Land Buddhism and the Shorter Sukhāvātyūha Sūtra

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, Inner Asia, South Asia, Central Asia, Japan, India, China, Tibet, Taiwan, Hong Kong, Sri Lanka

The map covers the historical regions presumably once influenced by the Shorter Sukhāvātyūha Sūtra and Pure Land Buddhism. Many areas are no longer

occupied by self-identified Buddhists, such as Central Asia and Northern India. Since Pure Land Buddhism has been developed into a "world religion," I would not count the Non-Asian area with scattered Pure Land practitioners.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Gómez, Luis O. *Land of Bliss: The Paradise of the Buddha of Measureless Light: Sanskrit and Chinese Versions of the Sukhāvātīvyūha Sūtras*. Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, 1996.
- Source 2: Jones, Charles B. *Chinese Pure Land Buddhism: Understanding a Tradition of Practice*. Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, 2019.
- Source 3: Kim, Young-Jae. "Reconstructing Pure Land Buddhist Architecture in Ancient East Asia." *Religions* 12, no. 9 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel12090764>.

Notes: Müller, Friedrich Max, and Bunyiu Nanjio. *Sukhāvātī-Vyūha: Description of Sukhāvātī, the Land of Bliss*. Vol. 1. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1883. Payne, Richard Karl, and Kenneth Kazuo Tanaka. *Approaching the Land of Bliss: Religious Praxis in the Cult of Amitābha*. Vol. 17. University of Hawaii Press, 2004. Tanaka, Kenneth K. *The Dawn of Chinese Pure Land Buddhist Doctrine: Ching-Ying Hui-Yuan's Commentary on the Visualization Sutra*. Albany: SUNY Press, 1990. Yu, Jimmy. "Pure Land Devotion in East Asia." In *The Wiley Blackwell Companion to East and Inner Asian Buddhism*, 199–220. New York City: Wiley Blackwell, 2014. 信楽 峻麿 Shigaraki Takamaro. "阿弥陀仏論 (A Study of Amida Buddha)." *竜谷大学仏教文化研究所紀要*, no. 20 (1982): p98-127. 孙伯君 Sun Bojun. "The Tangut Translation of the Amitabha Sutra 《佛说阿弥陀经》的西夏译本." *Tangut Studies 西夏研究*, no. 1 (2011): 23–32. 小林 良信 Kobayashi Ryoshin. "『阿弥陀経』について (On Amiba Sutra)." *印度學佛教學研究 Indogaku Bukkyogaku Kenkyu* 39, no. 2 (1991): 913–908. 王尧 Wang Yao. "The Fourth Installment of Critical Comparison Between Tibetan and Chinese Buddhist Canon--The Amitabha Sutra 藏汉佛典对勘释读之四——《佛说阿弥陀经》." *Tibet Studies 西藏研究*, no. 4 (1990): 64–70. 芮樱 Rui Ying. "Study on the Repair of the Mural Illustration of the Amitabha Sutra in the No. 372 Mogao Cave 莫高窟第 372 窟阿弥陀经变壁画残缺部分复原探究." *Chinese Academy of Fine Arts 中国美术学院*, 2014.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://jsinternational.org/>
- Source 1 Description: The Official Website of Jodo Shinshu
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.lionsroar.com/the-history-of-pure-land-buddhism/>
- Source 2 Description: Article of Pure Land Buddhism published by Lion's Roar
- Source 3 URL: <https://tricycle.org/beginners/decks/pure-land/>
- Source 3 Description: Buddhist Studies lesson given by Tricycle

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: http://tripitaka.cbeta.org/T12n0366_001
- Source 1 Description: The CBETA edition of the Amitabha Sutra translated by Kumārajīva

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked

– with Ink

Notes: It is utterly unclear in which format the text was initially composed. Early Buddhist sutras are transmitted orally and then recorded on palm leaves. However, Amitabha Sutra emerged relatively late, after the popularization of paper. It is likely that it first appears as writing on sheet materials, such as hemp paper, parchment, or palm leaf.

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

– Specify: Initially, the text was most likely written on hemp paper. Then, in China, it was copied on silk, bamboo slips, and mass produced paper.

Notes: We essentially do not know how the initial manuscript was made. But considering the historical circumstance (1-2 century Central Asia), hemp paper was already invented and there were no palm leaves in the area. Hemp paper is the best guess. Later in East Asia, it was copied upon multiple materials, including paper, silk, and bamboo slips. Paper is the most popular media.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Ritual preparation

Notes: One needs to cleanse the body and mind, recites scriptural passages/dharanis before copying the sutra.

Reference: Shinohara, Koichi. *Spells, Images, and Mandalas*. Columbia University Press, 2014.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Spells_Images_and_Mandalas.html?hl=&id=1nbeAwAAQBAJ.

Reference: Berkwitz, Stephen C., Juliane Schober, and Claudia Brown. *Buddhist Manuscript Cultures*. Routledge, 2009. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=8gl6AgAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Kucera, Karil J.. *Ritual and Representation in Chinese Buddhism*. Cambria Press, 2016.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=fVpzCwAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Lowe, Bryan D.. *Ritualized Writing*. University of Hawaii Press, 2017.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=xIkEAAAQBAJ>.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: No. The text remains the same as in the canon.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Notes: Generally, no. It is because a large portion of believers and practitioners are laities, who may store the text wherever they want. Also, many may carry the sutra as a protective amulet.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Yes

Notes: For individual believers, the sutra is usually stored with images of Sukhavati paintings and the portraits of Amitabha and Guanyin. Sometimes, people will place statues of the Pure Land trinity with the scripture.

↳ Where is iconography or imagery present?

Select all that apply

- At home
- Religious space with restricted access
- Some public spaces

Notes: Usually, the sutra is accompanied by the image of Sukhavati and its trinity, the Amitabha Buddha, Avalokiteśvara Bodhisattva, and Mahasthamaprapta Bodhisattva. The sutra sometimes contains a drawing of Sukhavati as well. In East Asian Buddhist monasteries, statues of the Pure Land trinity are virtually everywhere, as well as the copies of Amitabha Sutra.

↳ Are there distinct or notable features or attributes in the religious group's iconography or images?

– Yes

Notes: A range of creatures, as the manifestation of Amitabha's Dharma, exist in his Pure Land. Thus, based on Pure Land scriptures, these creatures are depicted in the painting of Sukhavati.

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: There are birds, not normal birds but the embodiment and the preacher of dharma, existing in the Pure Land.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: The Pure Land Trinity, images or iconographies of Amitābha with the Avalokiteśvara and Mahāsthāmaprāpta bodhisattvas.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: Usually, in the painting of Sukhavati, the sentient beings who are reborn there are nourished in lotus flowers and to be born from the buds.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Status objects (tools, weapons, mounts, throne, etc.)

– Yes

Notes: The images usually contain pagodas, various divine instruments, and palaces.

↳ Humans

– No

Notes: No one is technically a "human" but only in human shapes.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: Being reborn in a lotus flower is definitely a supernatural narrative. There other types of images that contain the narrative that Guanyin (Avalokiteśvara) receives the deceased to the land of Sukhavati.

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Specify

–Specify: There are perhaps many other types of images associated to the Amitabha Sutra and Sukhavati. However, the most common is the painting of Sukhavati with the Pure Land Trinity, various devine beings, and those who are reborn in the lotus buds.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Notes: The best answer is no, in my view. Pure Land Buddhism has very distinct iconographies, especially the images of Amitabha and Avalokiteśvara. Although these beings have different Rewarded Bodies, as they are displayed visually, they are easily recognized in their own cultural setting. Their images are very iconic.

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: Pure Land Buddhism is largely a diffused, popular religious tradition. The production of the text is primarily driven by two factors, the accumulation of merits and the spread of Dharma. Individual believers, either lay or monastic, tend to copy the sutras themselves as a devotional and meritorious practice. The monasteries also mass-produce the sutra. Nowadays, the Amitabha sutra is freely distributed in East Asia temples. Nonetheless, these acts are mostly voluntary and not funded by any polity. The only exception may be Kamakura Buddhism, when the feudal government is politically backed up by different sects of Buddhism. During this time, the production of the Amitabha Sutra perhaps was funded by the feudal government.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

Notes: The text is canonical in East Asia. Since the emergence of the Buddhist catalog, its canonicity has been certified. It is No.366 in the 12th volume of the Taisho canon. See http://jinglu.cbeta.org/cgi-bin/oldjinglu.pl?lang=en&utra_name=%E9%98%BF%E5%BD%8C%E9%99%80%E7%B6%93&utra_dynasty=&utra_byline=&catalog=&sh

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Yes

Notes: Though the sutra itself is not often recited, the most popular Pure Land practice, the recital of the Buddha's name, allegedly originates from the sutra. For the performance of nianfo (recite the Buddha's name), see examples like <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EiebnqBBxzQ> and <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XrwlLyc24a4>

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god?

– Yes

Notes: The Amitabha Sutra gives its origin story itself, just as most other Buddhist sutras. In Jeta's grove, the Buddha preached the message--his Dharma--to the assembly. Besides, it is a tricky question whether we can identify Buddha as a high god or not. In the public perception, Buddha can be seen as a high god, especially in Mahayana Buddhism.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Inspired by high god?

– No

Notes: In a sense, it is the Amitabha Buddha and his Pure Land that inspired the Sakyamuni Buddha to preach about Sukhavati. However, we may also say it is the Sakyamuni Buddha who, out of his own compassion and for the benefit of sentient beings, preaches the Sukhavati to the dwellers in the Saha world. In my opinion, it is not the Amitabha Buddha who "inspired" the Sakyamuni Buddha. From an emic perspective, We may see the Sakyamuni simply providing an alternative method to nirvana.

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– No

Notes: The canonicity of the scripture comes from its invariability. The Amitabha Sutra is one of the most important Pure Land texts. In comparison, all of its commentaries can be seen as alterable, but the Amitabha sutra is very essential.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: When we are discussing the commentary tradition, I can only infer the East Asian Pure Land Buddhism, where Pure Land is a strong-held living tradition with distinct practices and textual foundations.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?

– Yes

Notes: Normally, Buddhist monastics have the rightful skills and authority to interpret the scriptures. The Wikipedia page of the sutra lists its 24 commentaries, see <https://zh.wikipedia.org/zh-hans/%E4%BD%9B%E8%AA%AA%E9%98%BF%E5%BD%8C%E9%99%80%E7%B6%93> Among these 24 commentaries, some are made by laities. Usually, lay people can also make interpretations and scholastic debates about seminal Buddhist scriptures. These lay interpretations can easily spread in the lay practitioners' social circle.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?

– No

↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)

– No

Notes: There might be minor disagreements, such as the specific requirements for the Pure Land rebirth, the nuanced ritual procedures, and technical scholastic debates. The biggest difference exists between the Japanese sectarianized Pure Land school and Chinese diffused practitioners. Japanese and Chinese conceive different patriarchs of the Pure Land tradition. However, there is no conflict and people usually respect this difference. Also, it has nothing to deal with the Amitabha Sutra per se. Overall, there is no common disagreement in the East Asian Pure Land tradition. In Japan, there are sectarian divisions between Jodo Shu and Jodo Shinshu. However, for the Amitabha Sutra, both sects hold similar views.

↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?

– No

Notes: Since there is little major disagreement, there is little resolving debate.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: Everyone is welcomed to transmit the scripture, but the monastic are the professionals.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– No

Notes: No. East Asian Buddhism has both Bhikkhu Sangha and Bhikkhuni Sangha, which encompass the female and male genders. There is no gender exclusion rule.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– No

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– No

Notes: Buddhism, as a social institution, historically encourages translations and localizations. People can teach, preach, write, and copy the sutra in the language they wish.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

Reference: Wu, Jiang, and Greg Wilkinson. *Reinventing the Tripitaka*. Lexington Books, 2017. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=m084DwAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Lopez, Donald S.. *Buddhist Scriptures*. Penguin UK, 2004. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=6Pd-2IIZip4C>.

Reference: Long, Darui, and Jinhua Chen. *Chinese Buddhist Canons in the Age of Printing*. Routledge, 2020. https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=_M3nDwAAQBAJ.

Reference: Storch, Tanya. *The History of Chinese Buddhist Bibliography: Censorship and Transformation of the Tripitaka*. Cambria Press, 2014. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=e7J5CgAAQBAJ>.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

Notes: Buddhism has its very specific meaning of Tripitaka. And the Amitabha sutra is contained in both Mahayana canons--the Tibetan and Chinese canons. Neither canon is permanently closed. The contained scriptures and the catalogs are changing constantly. The canonicity of some sutras are viewed differently sometimes.

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the cannon as it is currently understood?

– Yes

Notes: For example, CBETA has collected numerous commentaries of the Amitabha made by Chinese Buddhist masters. Some of them were made in the Qing dynasty and the Republic era.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: While Sanskrit is usually considered as the most sacred language in East Asian sources, many scholars have argued the sound is the most sacred. Buddhist sutras are written in different languages, and there is no distinct religious/sacred language, at least in the case of Mahayana Buddhism.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Total audience: 500000000

Notes: The worlddata.info, see <https://www.worlddata.info/religions/buddhism.php>, suggests there are 400 million Buddhists. According to the Pew Research Center, there are about 500 million Buddhists worldwide, see <https://www.pewresearch.org/religion/2012/12/18/global-religious-landscape-exec>. All

Buddhists are intended audience.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

– Number: 490000000

Notes: Again, according to the Pew Research Center, more than 98% percent of Buddhists are Asian.

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 0

Notes: Central Asian countries used to be culturally and religiously dominated by Mahayana Buddhism and the devotion to Amitabha. Nowadays, the number of Buddhists in these countries is nearly zero.

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 244000000

Notes: China reportedly has 244 million Buddhists, which counts up to 18.2% percent of its total population.

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: The rise of Islam is clearly the biggest influence. Indic Buddhism tantralized in response to the Islamic invasion, and Central Asian countries ceased practicing Buddhism. Also, the Communist anti-religion police also prohibited religious practices, including Pure Land Buddhism.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

– Number: 11.2

Notes: Based on the population of the sample region, which is roughly 4.3 billion, the percentage of Buddhists is about 11.2%

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 0

Notes: Again, Buddhism was extinct in Central Asia for centuries.

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 66.7

Notes: According to Statista, about 66.7 percent of Japanese self-proclaims believe in Buddhism, see <https://www.statista.com/statistics/237609/religions-in-japan/>

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: The rise of Islam and Communism.

↳ Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Notes: The intended audience of the scriptures is mostly Buddhists. Despite Buddhists trying to enforce conversion, in Asia, only a marginal number of people convert to Buddhism. The Buddhists, especially Mahayana Buddhists are the intended audience. The Mahayana groups in Southasia Asia also spread Mahayana Sutra, including the Amitabha Sutra, to the locals.

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

– No

Notes: While it is emically claimed that the sutra is intended for all sentient beings, Pure Land practitioners do not coerce their scriptures and teachings to everyone. The main targeted audience is those who at least have sprouted an interest in Buddhism. The monastic does not chant the sutra for non-willing participants. And copying sutras are done by self-identified Buddhists as always.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

Notes: While Buddhism is a missionary religion, the Amitabha Sutra does not contain any passage that encourages active proselytization.

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– No

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

Notes: As mentioned above, the sutra per se does not contain any passage about spreading the Dharma. The sutra only emphasizes it is the best method to achieve nirvana, because it is easy and blissful.

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

Notes: Buddhism, in general, does not proselytize by coercion.

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– No

Notes: Interpretively, the answer may be "yes," since potentially helping other sentient beings to achieve nirvana is an encouraging wholesome deed. However, there is no straightforward passage that justify the normative proselytization activity.

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– Yes

↳ Does proselytization take place regardless of the fact that the text is silent on the matter?

– Yes

Notes: The Pure Land Buddhists will often chant for non-Buddhists. In a way, they are culturally proselytizing the Pure Land doctrines without being explicit about it. Both

the cleric and laypeople love to explain the Pure Land ideals to newcomers.

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Notes: There are some historical trajectories of the Pure Land tradition in Asia. From the belief in Amitabha to the popularization of the nianfo practice, all changes are cultural and gradual. The formations of Japanese Pure Land schools, to an extent, are predicated on the Japanese socio-political situation. These schools claim their orthodoxy but it was not done by "reform to the correct interpretation."

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Notes: It is another tricky question, whose answer is predicated on the definition of "text in question." In general, no. The Pure Land Rituals based on its core scriptures, including the Amitabha Sutra, are solidly established in Asia. No dubious text will be employed. However, there may be the case that, seeing Pure Land as a Chinese popular practice, texts from other traditions will be used together. In this case, from a Buddhist standpoint, the non-orthodox texts are the texts in question.

Is there material significance to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Pure Land rituals involve numerous materials around the texts, such as incense, the incense burner, and a mat for meditation. Also, in general, Buddhist scriptures are usually preserved especially. Individuals can store the sutra in a small wooden box. A monastery usually has its own facility, as such Sutra Storage Hall, for storing the sutras. Sometimes, in both East and Inner Asia, people will put sutras in a revolving repository. It is believed turning the repository has the same benefits as reciting the sutra. Sometimes, a sutra can also be used as an amulet. People can have their miniature sutra copies and carry them always.

Reference: Wu, Jiang, and Greg Wilkinson. *Reinventing the Tripitaka*. Lexington Books, 2017.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=m084DwAAQBAJ>.

↳ Is it visible?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the sutra are visual written text.

↳ Is it hidden?

– No

↳ Can it be touched?

– Yes

Notes: One can hold it to read it, study it, or copy it.

↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?

– No

- ↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?
 - No
 - Notes: Amitabha is mostly an exoteric tradition. There might be some esoteric connotation in the late Tantric movement, but not very prevalent.
- ↳ Does the text serve a protective function?
 - Yes
- ↳ Does the text serve a healing function?
 - No
 - Notes: Unless we call nirvana the ultimate cure, the Amitabha Sutra is not intended to heal sentient beings.
- ↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?
 - No
- ↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?
 - No
- ↳ Does the text serve as an incantation?
 - No
 - Notes: It is the case for the other two Pure Land texts, of which parts can be used as incantations. However, the Amitabha Sutra is short and do not have the function.
- ↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?
 - No
- ↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?
 - No
 - Notes: The text is well-circulated and it was mostly hand-copied or printed on paper. There was no major change of medium and there was no debate.
- ↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?
 - No
- ↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?

Please specify the substances in the sub-questions

 - Yes
 - Notes: Incense and the images/iconographies of the Pure Land Trinity are mostly accompanied. Sometimes, people also offer food.
 - ↳ Liquids?
 - No

↳ Solids?

– Yes

↳ Vapors or smoke?

– No

↳ Burnt offering?

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Often the text is accompanied by the images, statues, or other types of iconographies of the Pure Land trinity.

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

Notes: At least in East Asia, the copying of the sutra is a practice of calligraphy itself. Many times, the sutra is a calligraphy art. In addition, some illustrator may draw the images of the Amitabha Buddha and/or the Pure Land along with the sutra.

↳ Calligraphy?

– Yes

↳ Illustrations?

– Yes

↳ Illuminations?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Let alone the modern translations, at the very least, there are original Sanskrit manuscripts, three Chinese translations, and a Tibetan translation. All these translations are seen as proper, though some are no longer extant and some only survived in fragments.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

Notes: The differentiation is due to the multiple translations and their respectively used languages. Translated in different eras and done by different teams, the translation

style and exact wordings also vary, but the overall messages and ritual usages remain the same.

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

Notes: It might be one of the most significant difference, since all translations are done in different time period and used different languages.

↳ Content of text?

– No

Notes: The content of the text varies very little. It may due to the translation skill and style.

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

Notes: No ritually difference between different translations.

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Notes: There is little debate about which version is proper. The problem is not only which version has the best translation quality but also which version is extant and accessible. In East Asia, the most accessible version is translated by Kumarajiva, which is also believed as the most elegantly translated one.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The text is first collected in Tibetan and Chinese canons. Then, by Japanese and Chinese Buddhists, the scriptures with clear Pure Land motifs are collected together as the Pure Land classics.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

Notes: There is no longer a Sanskrit canon now, so I am referring to the Tibetan and Chinese canon. The authority is listed by many different standards, including the original Sanskrit manuscripts, the credibility of the translators, and the translation skills. Skillful and knowledgeable compilers would know the internal qualities of a believed authentic original scriptures and put it in the canon.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, as I answered above, Buddhist canons are usually open canon.

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– No

Notes: The authority, authenticity, and canonicity of the Amitabha Sutra is rarely

challenged.

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

Notes: The Amitabha Sutra is one of the shortest Pure Land sutras. It is individually translated and categorized.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Notes: The text is very explicitly a canonical scripture.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary? (Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Notes: It is best described that the text includes a ritual manual, despite being very short and succinct. One needs to become peacefully mindful of the Buddha for seven days before death. 舍利弗！不可以少善根福德因緣，得生彼國。舍利弗！若有善男子、善女人，聞說阿彌陀佛，執持名號，若一日、若二日、若三日、若四日、若五日、若六日、若七日，一心不亂。其人臨命終時，阿彌陀佛與諸聖眾現在其前。是人終時，心不顛倒，即得往生阿彌陀佛極樂國土。舍利弗！我見是利，故說此言。若有眾生聞是說者，應當發願生彼國土。

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: The text does not contain any lineage or lineage chart.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: The text is basically the advocacy of Amitabha's Pure Land. It is not legally abiding and does not have any legal implications.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: No religious calendar nor any dating is provided in the text.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: It is not a topic in the text.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The whole practice and belief of Pure Land Buddhism is predicated on the afterlife in Sukhavati.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: The location of the Sukhavati is not specific, and even perhaps is not "spatial." Sukhavati does not exist in our cosmos but is another cosmos vaguely described as located in the west.

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: The Amitabha Sutra does not state the temporality of life in Sukhavati. Other Pure Land texts, such as the Contemplation Sutra, offer some hints. The timespan that you spend in Sukhavati is depended on one's past karma and spiritual capability. After becoming prepared to spread the teaching, one goes to other cosmos to teach Buddhism

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Notes: No such debate exists in the text.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Notes: The text is explicit about reincarnation in Sukhavati. Although Buddhism generally believes in the doctrine of reincarnation (in samsara), it is not discussed in this text per se.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Notes: No such instruction is given.

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Notes: The text does not talk about burial nor sacrifices.

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Notes: The text does not mention burial and burial procedures.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Notes: The text is not about funerary practice.

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: To be specific, the text lists hundreds of Buddhas and Bodhisattvas. Together, they recommend the listeners to take refuges in Amitabha's Pure Land.

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: It is again a problem of definition. Pure Land is a very unique Buddhist tradition and I am accepting Amitabha and his attendants as high gods for many reasons. First, Sukhavati is the land created and maintained by the dharmic power of Amitabha. Along with his attendants, the Pure Land trinity has the definitive power and dictates everything in their Western Pure Land. Second, Bodhisattvas like Guanyin have salvific powers. These enlightened beings can react to the praying of residents of the Saha World. Whenever believers recite the names of Amitabha and Guanyin, their calls will be received. According to the Pure Land tradition, Buddhist believers can be saved by the Pure Land trinity's miraculous powers. Third, for those who are reborn in the Sukhavati, one can gain significant salvific progress (as the benefit of living in the "Pure" Land) and one is guaranteed on a speedy track to nirvana. In these senses, the power of Pure Land divinities is not limited to psychic powers obtained through magics and meditations. Thus, Amitabha and his attendants can be seen as supreme high gods.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

–Specify: The Amitabha Buddha is extremely powerful and compassionate.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– No

Notes: It is not a relevant question since Amitabha is from Sukhavati. Presumably, he knows everything in his cosmos but not everything in the Saha world.

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Can reward

– Yes

Notes: Amitabha can bring devotees to Sukhavati.

↳ Can punish

– No

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– No

Notes: The Buddhas and Bodhisattvas have no emotions nor feelings. They have transcended these worldly qualities.

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– No

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– Yes

Notes: Absolutely yes. But advocated by the text, the best and easiest option is devoting to Amitabha.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: The Buddha represents Dharma. He possess the ultimate truth.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Notes: Though not specified in the text, the Pure Land Trinity can communicate with believers. They may appear in the manifested body, in the dream, or rewarded body.

↳ In waking, everyday life
– Yes

↳ In dreams
– Yes

↳ In trance possession
– No

↳ Through divination practices
– No

↳ Only through religious specialists
– No

↳ Only through monarch
– No

↳ Other form of communication with living
– Yes

Notes: Being mindful of the Buddha. Recalling the Buddha's name and form. Meditation.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
– Yes

Notes: In a certain way, yes, because the text teaches the method of being reborn in Sukhavati. It advocates the practice of being mindful of the Buddha.

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?
– No

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?
– No

↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?
– No

↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?
– No

↳ What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).
– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Notes: The Pure Land reborners are spirits. They have physical bodies. The text has nothing to do with the spirits.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: There are supernatural beings manifested by Amitabha's Dharma. They are shaped like bird but are technically not living beings. 復次舍利弗！彼國常有種種奇妙雜色之鳥——白鵠、孔雀、鸚鵡、舍利、迦陵頻伽、共命之鳥。是諸眾鳥，晝夜六時出和雅音，其音演暢五根、五力、七菩提分、八聖道分如是等法。其土眾生聞是音已，皆悉念佛、念法、念僧。舍利弗！

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Notes: Yes, they can be seen by dwellers of Sukhavati.

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

Notes: One can hear their sounds and feel their presence.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– No

Notes: They are the beings in Sukhavati and shall know nothing about the Saha world.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: These beings only preach Dharma to the dwellers of the Sukhavati but impose no casual effect on beings in the Saha world.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

Notes: It is more like one way communication from these bird-like beings to Pure Land Dwellers.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

Notes: These beings have transcended worldly emotions and feelings.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: They are the representation and manifestation of Amitabha's Dharma. They are teaching Buddhism constantly.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Notes: The sutra lists Buddhas and Bodhisattvas from the six directions. All the Buddhas and Bodhisattvas attest to the miraculous effects of Sukhavati. They can be seen as a pantheon. For example, 舍利弗！南方世界有日月燈佛、名聞光佛、大焰肩佛、須彌燈佛、無量精進佛，如是等恒河沙數諸佛，各於其國出廣長舌相，遍覆三千大千世界，說誠實言：『汝等眾生，當信是稱讚不可思議功德一切諸佛所護念經。舍利弗！西方世界有無量壽佛、無量相佛、無量幢佛、大光佛、大明佛、寶相佛、淨光佛，如是等恒河沙數諸佛，各於其國出廣長舌相，遍覆三千大千世界，說誠實言：『汝等眾生，當信是稱讚不可思議功德一切諸佛所護念經。』

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– No

Notes: Though Buddha is the head of the assembly, there is no formal hierarchy in each world.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

Notes: It is somehow true. Each Buddha has its own cosmos, and they supposedly only preach to and save the sentient beings in their cosmos.

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: No other organization of pantheon.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: There are beings manifested by the Buddha' Dharma. They are not real individualist beings but the preachers of the Dharma.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: The text does not offer any divination method.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: An essential idea of Amitabha's Sukhavati is that, upon hearing the request of his follower, Amitabha or his attendant will be able to appear and assist the individuals who called for help. The Buddhas and Bodhisattvas are enlightened beings with supernormal powers, including the divine eyes and the divine ears. They are able to monitor the situation if someone calls for the help, for reciting a prayer or being mindful of the image of the Buddha/Bodhisattva. In essence, being escorted to the Sukhavati at the moment of death can only be done on the premise of spiritual monitoring.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular
– No

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?
– No
Notes: Despite rituals being needed, offerings are unnecessary. The Buddhas and Bodhisattvas help sentient beings unconditionally.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
– No
Notes: Killing is prohibited as one of the five main precepts of Buddhism. However, even though one who had violated the crime, one can also be reborn in the Pure Land.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
– No
Notes: Adultery is against the five basic Buddhist precepts. However, adulterers can obtain a Sukhavati reborn as well.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
– No
Notes: Another problem with the five precepts. It is not a problem here.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
– No
Notes: As long as one is not speaking against Buddhism, it would be enough. No oath is taken place.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
– No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes
 - Notes: Ritual, though very easy, is quintessential here. One needs to be mind of the Buddha Amitabha or his attendant Bodisavattvas.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - Yes
 - Notes: Yes, one needs to be mindful of the Buddha.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other
 - Specify: Those who violated the five greatest sins cannot be reborn in Sukhavati, including killing father, mother, arhats, causing disharmony in sangha, and hurting the Buddha.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: No punishment will be given. It is solely about bringing salvation to the mass public.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The biggest and the most direct reward is being reborn in Sukhavati. In this land of ultimate bliss, all sufferings cease and one will eventually reach enlightenment.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

Notes: The creation of and escort to the Pure Land is solely caused by Amitabha's bodhisattva vows. He once vowed to create such a Pure Land before becoming a Buddha, and now he is the Buddha and the land is created. Also, he vowed to assist sentient beings who requested help. In this respect, Sukhavati is solely based on Amitabha's original vows and his compassion.

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

Notes: Another problem with the definition. If we see Amitabha as a "high god," the answer is surely yes.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

Notes: Although the Amitabha Buddha is powerful, one still needs to be faithful to him and practice the rituals. In this sense, the successful rebirth in Sukhavati is determined by this impersonal devotion and practice.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the answer shall be the same with the prior one.

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

Notes: Being selfless is not a prerequisite of being reborn in Sukhavati.

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Yes

Notes: The reward is otherworldly and is done at the moment of death via reincarnate in

Amitabha's Sukhavati.

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: Later, Buddhists normally believe being reborn in Sukhavati is the easiest way to secure enlightenment. The idea of dharma decay is prominent, and the spiritual capability of sentient beings is sufficient to redeem themselves from the Saha world. One needs to rely on the power of Amitabha.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

Notes: The idea of sensory pleasure is largely irrelevant. From a Mahayana perspective, all sensory experience is ultimately empty. The afterlife is not consisted of pleasure but the spiritual cultivation and preparation for becoming the Buddha.

↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?

– No

Notes: It is hard to describe the ultimate goal of Pure Land Buddhism as happiness. Happiness is transient and illusory. The goal is to awake from this illusory reality and reach the Buddhahood.

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?

– Yes

Notes: Life in Sukhavati is definitely superior. All sufferings cease and one is no longer mentally afflicted by negative emotions.

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?

– Yes

Notes: Pure Land is definitively a superior realm. All the superior qualities of life in Sukhavati are bestowed by the Sukhavati itself.

↳ Other?

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– No

Notes: The reward is bestowed at the moment of death. And one needs to reincarnate to enjoy the fruition of it.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: In many respects, Amitabha is a messianic figure. His Pure Land is very distinctive in relation to

the Saha world. And the Sukhavati is the land of ultimate bliss, without any pain and suffering. Amitabha is the sole creator and benefactor of it. He is the most capable that no other Buddhas/Bodhisattvas can compete. Being reborn in Sukhavati is the simplest way to secure salvation.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: Amitabha is surely a messianic figure. However, for dwellers of the Saha world, there is neither a specific place nor an exact time about Amitabha comes and saves the entire sentient beings. The salvation is largely individual and one is required to devote to Amitabha for one's own rebirth in Sukhavati.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

Notes: Amitabha chooses to do it because of his compassion. He not only wants himself to get away from the samsara but wishes to facilitate others.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– No

Notes: There is no political order in the land of Sukhavati. All beings and objects there are actually the manifestation of Amitabha's Dharma.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– Yes

Notes: In certain ways, yes. Amitabha is a Buddha, who teaches and preaches the way of nirvana. Sukhavati is the place the prepare those who are reborn there to be bodhisattvas themselves and go to other worlds to spread the Dharma.

↳ Other purpose

– Specify: The most direct purpose is to have people get way from the Saha world and all sufferings there.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Notes: The Amitabha Sutra does not specify any eschatology. It does not mention the decay of Dharma. Such Pure Land Eschatology is very prominent in other Pure Land sutras, such as the Contemplation Sutra.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: The Amitabha Sutra does not prescribe any social norms. It is about individual practice, instead of communal behaviors.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Notes: The text does not make any moral requirement nor distinction. In reserve, it emphasizes the possibility of universal salvation. One gains salvation regardless of one's past actions.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Notes: "Virtue" is not a precise term to describe what is advocated by the text. "Devotion" can be a much better word choice. The text do not regulate one's moral behaviors nor values.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The text does not require any ascetic practice. The only requirement is single-mindedly being mindful of the Buddha. A monastic require celibacy but most of the Pure Land Buddhists are laities.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: Abstinence of sexual activities is not prescribed by the text.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Notes: No mention of castration is found in the text.

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Notes: The text does not talk about fasting.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: It is generally required, for East Asian Buddhists, to adopt a vegetarian diet. However, even though one violated this precept, one can still be reborn in Sukhavati. Thus, the forgone of the food opportunity is not required.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Notes: Body modification is not found in the text.

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Notes: It actually depends on whether meditation, either seated or walking, is painful. For meditators, meditation is usually not considered painful.

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Notes: The text has no content about sacrifice.

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Notes: One does not need to make any sacrifice to be reborn in Sukhavati.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Notes: Being mindful of the Amitabha Buddha is not physically risky.

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: The most fundamental precept would be accepting the authority of Buddhism. One has to believe in the Buddha, and pay respect to Buddha, Sangha, and Dharma.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Notes: The text advocates universal salvation. One does not exclude other people from the Buddhist community.

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Notes: Being mindful of the Buddha is essentially a small, private ritual. The ritual efficacy is limited to the performer.

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 1

Notes: Despite being unspecified by the Amitabha Sutra, other sutras require to repeat the practice of being mindful of the Buddha. It does not require a fixed interval of time between performances. One is free to choose when and how long to practice, as long as one's mind remains undisturbed. It is an estimate that the average interval is one hour.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Notes: No large, societal level, large ritual is needed.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Notes: There is no kinship terminology used in the text.

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Notes: The text is very serious. It is about the personal and eventually universal salvation, but about entertaining.

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: Pure Land, as the sacred space, does not need any sacrifice or offering to maintain. It is created by the votive power of the Amitabha Buddha.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A band

Notes: For the spread of Pure Land sutras, the social institutions created around them are best described as bands with no clear hierarchy and leadership. People usually follow the Pure Land teaching autonomously and there is no forced conversion. Power is largely regional and sectarian (in Japan). One gains its leading status by the proficient knowledge about the Pure Land Buddhism and professional activities, such as writing commentaries and preaching. There are no rigid rules determining everything.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A band

Notes: As I mentioned before, the production of Amitabha Sutra, just like most other Buddhist sutras, is led by two major channels. The first is individual sutra copiers who copy the sutra by hand and distribute (or keep the sutra themselves) as their wish. The second is the organized mass printing led by the monastery. Either way, the production team can be described as a "band," since all actions are voluntary and there is no social hierarchy in the production procedure.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– An empire

Notes: The destruction of the Amitabha Sutra is part of the historical persecutions of Buddhism. There are four major historical persecutions of Buddhism in pre-modern China, see https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Four_Buddhist_Persecutions_in_China, and another one led by the modern Communist regime. The destruction of text would also be found in Central Asia and Japan, where, respectively, the Islamic empire and the Meiji reformist government persecuted Buddhism institutionally.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Notes: The text is a Mahayana Pure Land sutra, which means it is almost exclusively done with salvific practices--practicing certain rituals and techniques in order to secure rebirth in Sukhavati and reach nirvana. The text does not mention famine, poverty, or care for the elderly and infirm. Of course, all human sufferings are absent in the Pure Land, including famine and poverty. However, there is nothing to be achieved in this Saha World, and nothing is institutionalized relieving.

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Notes: The text is a Mahayana Pure Land sutra, which means it is almost exclusively done with salvific practices--practicing certain rituals and techniques in order to secure rebirth in Sukhavati and reach nirvana. The text does not mention famine, poverty, or care for the elderly and infirm. Of course, all human sufferings are absent in the Pure Land, including famine and poverty. However, there is nothing to be achieved in this Saha World, and nothing is institutionalized relieving.

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Notes: The text is a Mahayana Pure Land sutra, which means it is almost exclusively done with salvific practices--practicing certain rituals and techniques in order to secure rebirth in Sukhavati and reach nirvana. The text does not mention famine, poverty, or care for the elderly and infirm. Of course, all human sufferings are absent in the Pure Land, including famine and poverty. However, there is nothing to be achieved in this Saha World, and nothing is institutionalized relieving.

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: From a Buddhist perspective, being able to learn the Dharma, securing the rebirth in Sukhavati, and becoming enlightened are the best and most important "welfares." We may characterize it as the "spiritual welfare" that helps sentient beings eliminating all the sufferings.

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in both pre-modern and modern times, Buddhist monasteries are the place where sutra and their commentaries are taught. Amitabha is a popular sutra and, no exception, is taught in the temple.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Notes: No. The text mentions nothing about the teaching and promulgation of the scripture.

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Notes: The main theme and purpose of the text are intrinsically religious. The Amitabha Sutra is exclusively used for Pure Land Buddhist education, very rarely for secular audiences.

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Notes: No, the text is dedicated to both religious professionals and lay believers. In East Asia, lay believers vastly outnumber the monastics.

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: The text contains no information about gender. Throughout history, the text was produced and circulated in mainly patriarchal societies. However, Mahayana traditions have both Bhikkhu and Bhikkuni Sanghas, and laities have Upāsaka and Upāsikā. The education is open to all Buddhists, regardless of gender.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Notes: The text contains no information about gender. Throughout history, the text was produced and circulated in mainly patriarchal societies. However, Mahayana traditions have both Bhikkhu and Bhikkuni Sanghas, and laities have Upāsaka and Upāsikā. The education is open to all Buddhists, regardless of gender.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Notes: Buddhist sutras are more akin to textbooks. There is little pedagogical information in the Amitabha Sutra. The text talks nothing about the teacher and the practical teaching of itself.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Notes: There is no worldly benefits, because all Buddhists ideally are strived for otherworldly benefits--nirvana and help saving other sentient beings.

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Notes: There is no mention of bureaucracy in the text.

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Notes: The text has no explicit content about this-worldly public works.

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Notes: No mention of taxation in the text.

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Notes: Warfare is not discussed in the scripture.

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Notes: The text has nothing to deal with food production and disturbance.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Shorter Sukhāvātīyūha Sūtra, Gómez, Luis O.. Land of Bliss: The Paradise of the Buddha of Measureless Light: Sanskrit and Chinese Versions of the Sukhāvātīyūha Sutras. Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, n.d..

Reference: Shorter Sukhāvātīyūha Sūtra, Payne, Richard Karl, and Kenneth Kazuo Tanaka. Approaching the Land of Bliss. University of Hawaii Press, 2004.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Approaching_the_Land_of_Bliss.html?hl=&id=tFcy_5UItqQC.

Reference: Shorter Sukhāvātīyūha Sūtra, Jones, Charles B.. Pure Land. Shambhala Publications, 2021.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Pure_Land.html?hl=&id=4ksqEAAAQBAJ.

Reference: Shorter Sukhāvātīyūha Sūtra, Jones, Charles B.. Chinese Pure Land Buddhism. University of Hawaii Press, 2019.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Chinese_Pure_Land_Buddhism.html?hl=&id=iFzGDwAAQBAJ.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Chinese_Pure_Land_Buddhism.html?hl=&id=iFzGDwAAQBAJ.

Reference: Shorter Sukhāvātīyūha Sūtra, Poceski, Mario. The Wiley Blackwell Companion to East and Inner Asian Buddhism. John Wiley & Sons, 2014.

<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=5i3qAgAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Shorter Sukhāvātīyūha Sūtra, Tanaka, Kenneth K., and Kenneth Kenichi Tanaka. The Dawn of Chinese Pure Land Buddhist Doctrine. SUNY Press, 1990.

https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Dawn_of_Chinese_Pure_Land_Buddhist_D.html?hl=&id=jhKVXrkVIZsC.

https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Dawn_of_Chinese_Pure_Land_Buddhist_D.html?hl=&id=jhKVXrkVIZsC.

Reference: Shorter Sukhāvātīyūha Sūtra, Pas, Julian F., Julian F. Pas, and Shan-Tao-Ta-Shih. Visions of Sukhavati. SUNY Press, 1995.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Visions_of_Sukhavati.html?hl=&id=Wjv85t5E0hQC.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Visions_of_Sukhavati.html?hl=&id=Wjv85t5E0hQC.

Reference: Shorter Sukhāvātīyūha Sūtra, Williams, Paul. Mahāyāna Buddhism. Psychology Press, 1989.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Mah%C4%81y%C4%81na_Buddhism.html?hl=&id=jrHilaUXmjkC.

Reference: Shorter Sukhāvātīyūha Sūtra, Cowell, Edward Byles, F. Max Muller, and J. Takakusu. Buddhist Mahayana Texts. Routledge, 2014.

<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=dzzKAgAAQBAJ>.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Yes, Wu, Jiang, and Greg Wilkinson. Reinventing the Tripitaka. Lexington Books, 2017.

<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=m084DwAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Ritual preparation, Shinohara, Koichi. Spells, Images, and Mandalas. Columbia University Press, 2014.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Spells_Images_and_Mandalas.html?hl=&id=InbeAwwAAQBAJ.

Reference: Ritual preparation, Berkwitz, Stephen C., Juliane Schober, and Claudia Brown. Buddhist Manuscript Cultures. Routledge, 2009.

<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=8gl6AgAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Ritual preparation, Kucera, Karil J.. Ritual and Representation in Chinese Buddhism. Cambria Press, 2016.

<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=fvpzCwAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Ritual preparation, Lowe, Bryan D.. Ritualized Writing. University of Hawaii Press, 2017. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=xlkEEAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Yes, Lopez, Donald S.. Buddhist Scriptures. Penguin UK, 2004. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=6Pd-2Iizp4C>.

Reference: Yes, Long, Darui, and Jinhua Chen. Chinese Buddhist Canons in the Age of Printing. Routledge, 2020. https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=_M3nDwAAQBAJ.

Reference: Yes, Storch, Tanya. The History of Chinese Buddhist Bibliography: Censorship and Transformation of the Tripitaka. Cambria Press, 2014. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=e7J5CgAAQBAJ>.